

Prevailing Ages in Acute, Recurrent and Chronic Urinary Tract Infections in Iraq, Kirkuk City

Fatma Mustafa Mohammed ✉

College of Dentistry / University of Tikrit, Iraq

Mahmood K. Saleh

Collage of Education for pure science ,Department of Biology,
University of Tikrit, Iraq

Abstract

Background: Acute, recurrent and chronic urinary tract infections are a major public health concern and occur in all age groups of males and females. They are a major and serious health problem that may lead to the subsequent development of serious symptoms with increased resistance to antibiotics.

Aim: This study aimed to identify the most vulnerable ages in acute, recurrent and chronic urinary tract infections and the most common age groups for infection in Kirkuk city

Materials and Methods: 151 urine samples were collected from patients with urinary tract infections who visited private clinics in Kirkuk Governorate. They were diagnosed by a urologist for the period from December 2022 to October 2023. The patients' ages ranged from 21-76 years. Microscopic examination, laboratory tests, culture and isolation of pathogens were performed to confirm the patients' cases.

Results: In the current study, the number of male patients with urinary tract infections was 62, representing 41.1%, while the number of females was 89, representing 58.9%. The condition was diagnosed as acute, recurrent, or chronic. The results of the current study showed, that the number of samples for patients with acute urinary tract infections was 91 samples, representing 60.3% for both males and females. The number of males was 37, representing 40.7%, and the number of females was 54, representing 3.59%. As for the cases of patients with recurrent urinary tract infections, the percentage of males was 42.6%, with 23, while the percentage of females was 57.4%, with 31 samples. As for patients with chronic urinary tract infections, the percentage of males was 33.3%, with 2, while the percentage of females was 66.7%, with 4 samples. As for the age groups most affected by these cases, the ages ranged between 42-51, where the numbers were 62, with a percentage of 41.1%, followed by the age group 21-32 years, where the numbers were 42, with a percentage of 28.8%. In general, female infections were higher than males.

Conclusion: This study, which was conducted on urinary tract patients in Kirkuk Governorate, showed that ages 42-51 years and ages 21-32 years are the most vulnerable groups to acute, chronic and recurrent urinary tract infections.

Introduction

The urinary system consists of organs, tubes, muscles, and nerves that work together to produce, store, and transport urine [1]. Urinary tract infections occur in all age groups, males and females [2]. Older males suffer

from urinary tract infections because most of them are exposed to prostatitis. Older women also suffer from hormonal changes due to aging and weak immunity [3]. Recurrent urinary tract infections are defined as urinary tract infections that occur at least three times in a 12-

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month period or at least twice in a six-month period [4]. Fifty percent of women experience an episode at some point in their lives, and 20 to 30% recur within 3 to 4 months of the acute infection [5].

Urinary tract infections are common and recurrent and can become chronic [6]. Chronic inflammation is known to be a factor that may develop into various types of cancer. Studies indicate that 20% of chronic cases lead to cancer in adults [7]. Persistent microbial infections are a rapidly expanding problem due to increasing antimicrobial resistance. This trend is particularly worrisome because of the increasingly appreciated role that Chronic inflammation may play a role in cancer and chronic inflammatory diseases [8].

Materials and Methods

Collection of Samples

151 urine samples were collected from patients with urinary tract infections who visited private clinics in Kirkuk Governorate. They were diagnosed by a urologist for the period from December 2012 to October 2022. The patients' ages ranged from 21-76 years. Microscopic examination, laboratory tests, culture and isolation of pathogens were performed to confirm the patients' cases.

1- Study area

This study was conducted in Kirkuk Governorate for patients visiting private clinics on Doctors Street.

2- Patient selection

The clinical cases required in this study were diagnosed by a urologist whether their condition was chronic, acute or recurrent. 151 samples were between 21-78 years old,

3-Exclusion and Inclusion Criteria

The samples that were studied were those whose condition was diagnosed by a specialist doctor, whether their infection was acute, recurrent or chronic, by observing the symptoms of the disease for women and men. The specific information was recorded on the questionnaire sheet accurately from each sample under study, where medical data was recorded. Information related to the socio-demographic characteristics was collected, which included age, gender and the clinical condition diagnosed by the doctor. As for the survey criteria, patients suffering from chronic diseases, blood pressure, diabetes, heart disease, asthma, pregnant women, immune diseases and immunosuppressive drugs (autoimmune disease) were included, as well as those taking treatment.

Where those suffering from lipid disorders, diabetes, high blood pressure, kidney, heart and artery diseases, various acute infections and liver diseases were excluded. And other chronic diseases as these cases were exclusion criteria for this study

Individuals who are currently taking or have previously taken antibiotics or any other medication during the past three months. 2- Individuals who were suffering from any systemic disease and pregnant/lactating women. 3- Individuals who were suffering from any other bacterial or viral infection.

4-Collecting urine samples

The samples were collected in sterilized screw-capped tubes. Patients were instructed on the correct method of collecting the sample in that the sample was collected from the middle of the urine (Clean-Catch-Midstream Urine) to avoid contamination with the natural flora present in this area

Five ml of urine sample was taken in a sterile, clean centrifuge tube and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 minutes. The sediment was then examined microscopically at high magnification for the presence of pus, red blood cells, epithelial cells, crystals and yeast cells.

Based on routine laboratory tests including Gram stain, some cultural characteristics and biochemical tests, isolates were identified and culture results were obtained to confirm the disease cases to be studied.

Results

Table 1: Numbers and Percentages of Samples by Gender

Gender	No	%
Male	62	41.1
Female	89	58.9
Total	151	100.0

In the current study, the number of male patients with urinary tract infections was 62, representing 41.1%, while the number of female patients was 89, representing 58.9%. The results indicate, as shown in Table 1, that the number of female patients with urinary tract infections is higher than the number of male patients. These results were consistent with a group of studies conducted in Kirkuk Governorate [9], where the percentage of males was 23.4% and females was 76.6%. Females are usually more susceptible to the risk of urinary tract infections than males due to the anatomical and physiological differences in the urinary system between males and females [10] and that the lack of estrogen contributes to the increase in infections in females. Births Pregnancy Methods of delivery Contraceptive membranes Frequent intrauterine examinations [11]. The prostate gland also contains a germicidal substance and zinc, which play a crucial role in killing microorganisms [12].

Table 2: Numbers and Percentages According to the Clinical Cases to be Studied

Gender	Study Group					
	Acute		Recurrent		Chronic	
	No	%	No	%	No	%
Male	37	40.7	23	42.6	2	33.3
Female	54	59.3	31	57.4	4	66.7
Total	91	100.0	54	100.0	6	100.0

Table 2 shows the clinical cases from which samples were collected for urinary tract patients. They were diagnosed by a urologist and based on the patients' clinical symptoms, laboratory tests and culture, the case was diagnosed as acute, recurrent or chronic. The results of the current study showed, as shown in the table above, that the number of samples for acute urinary tract patients was 91 samples, representing 60.3% for both males and females. The number of males was 37, representing 40.7%, and the number of females was 54, representing 59.3%. This is consistent with a study conducted by [13] that showed that 40-60% of women suffer from urinary tract infections once. It showed that 60% of women will develop acute infection. Females are more susceptible to acute infection, as it heals on its own within a few days and is still easy to treat with antibiotics. However, sometimes the infection may recur within weeks or months. 14 Pregnancy, childbirth, sexual activity, hormonal changes, menstruation and age Elias Immune status Genetic predisposition Unhealthy lifestyle Personal hygiene Weak innate or adaptive immune response Bacterial isolates and their virulence may also play a role in the development of acute urinary tract infections. As for the cases of patients and recurrent urinary tract infections, the percentage of males was 42.6% with 23 samples, while the percentage of females was 57.4% with 31 samples. Half of the women with recurrent urinary tract infections suffer from recurrence of infection within one year [13]. In a Canadian study, [14] out of 3085 people were exposed to urinary tract infections for more than one attack during the two-year period in which the study was conducted. They were exposed to 6 attacks in males [15]. Studies have also shown that recurrent urinary tract infections may occur due to a complete structural cause such as an enlarged prostate, an endoscope, or tools used in bladder endoscopy, a catheter, intestinal diseases, or congenital malformations [16]. Recurrent infection occurs with two attacks within 6 months or more than 3 attacks within [12]. Immunity also plays an important role in Recurrence of infection, for example, a decrease in TLR4, which is responsible for recognizing LPS in Gram-negative bacteria, and it has a role in the emergence of recurrent bacterial infections. The condition can develop from recurrent to chronic [17]. Therefore, caution must be taken when receiving treatment to prevent the development of the

condition, prevent kidney damage, prevent recurrence of infection, and strengthen the immune system. As for samples for patients with chronic urinary tract infection, the total number of samples was 6, and the number of males was 2 and females 4. The samples were very few due to the difficulty of diagnosis, as they require a very long period, and the period of collecting samples is not sufficient to obtain more numbers, as the difficulty of diagnosis does not respond to treatment and the difficulty of culturing bacteria. The results are 90% negative. The doctor relies on long-term treatment by giving antibiotics for 383 days, and it responds and may be cured. The percentage of males was 33.3%, with 2, while females had a percentage of 66.7%, with 4.

This study was consistent with [18], which showed that women suffer more than men in chronic urinary tract infection in many cases, and when not cared for, and treatment in the form Correct: Recurrent infection can turn into chronic infection, as chronic kidney patients are caused by recurrent infection [19]. Chronic kidney stones Urinary stones are a risk factor for treatment failure, as patients are more susceptible to many problems, so early management of urinary stones is important to prevent further subsequent infection, kidney damage, recurrent infection, and recurrent catheterization cases, which can lead to a chronic infection. Acute infections can also develop into chronic infections, as they colonize for weeks, months, or years. Uropathogenic infection also plays a role in chronic infection that lasts for months, and a history of infection is a major risk factor for chronic infection. Behavioral patterns of vaginal douching, failure to control recurrent infections, and weak immunity are all indicators that may help in the development of urinary tract infections and the deterioration of the patient's condition. In a study, it was shown that 84 of the patients' condition improved after 383 days of continuous treatment and reaching a resolution of symptoms [20], therefore, treatment was stopped in 221 patients whose condition deteriorated and some of them needed to be hospitalized and recovered after re-treatment. The development of the condition into a chronic one due to shortcomings in the diagnosis and development of the condition, mismanagement of previous attacks, and failure to adhere to the correct treatment may lead to a worsening of the condition and enhance bacterial resistance and circumvent the

immune system. Taking treatments accurately and not interrupting, i.e. following the doctor's instructions. Taking supplements may reduce strains that threaten to transform cases into chronic and recurrent ones. Prevention by taking supplements to treat recurrent urinary tract infections. It is preferable to refer patients to a center that has a special interest in urinary tract diseases and not to a general gynecology clinic.

Table 3: Numbers and Percentages by Age Group

Age Group	No	%
21-31	42	28.8
32-41	29	19.2
42-51	62	41.1
52-61	14	9.3
62-78	4	2.6
Total	151	100

Table 4: Numbers and Percentages by Age Groups in Males and Females

Age	Male		Female	
	No	%	No	%
21-31	18	29.0	24	26.9
32-41	12	19.4	17	19.4
42-51	23	37.1	39	37.1
52-61	6	9.7	8	9.7
62-78	3	4.8	1	4.8
Total	62	100.0	89	100.0

Discussion

In the current study, as shown in Table 3 and 4, the patient groups were divided according to age groups into five groups, which shows the prevalence of urinary tract infections in different age groups. The results of our study showed that the highest incidence of urinary tract infections was among the age groups 42-51, where the number was 62 and a percentage of 41.1%. This result was consistent with [21], which recorded a percentage of 39.3. The result also agreed with [22], where this group had the highest percentage of urinary tract infections. Age is one of the most important factors that play a major role in urinary tract infections, and the decline in the immune system with age plays a major role. The infection of females at advanced ages may be due to menopause and the accompanying hormonal changes, estrogen deficiency, vaginal atrophy, and vaginal prolapse [23]. The results also showed that the number of females was more than males because their anatomy makes them more susceptible, i.e. the physiology of the urinary system, pregnancy [24]. Also, the infection and its recurrence in childhood is a factor. Risk of chronic kidney disease and the decline of the immune system with age plays a major role in increasing infections at these ages [25]. Urinary tract infections increase at advanced ages and

one of the important reasons is prostate enlargement, loss of prostatic fluid and kidney stones. Prostate enlargement obstructs the flow of urine, which increases the risk of infection and the older are the most vulnerable due to their frequent hospitalization and weak immunity [26].

Also, the results showed that the age group 21-32 years was 42 and 82.8% and this result was consistent with [27] where its percentage was 58.9. It also agreed with Ismael 2022 [28] at 45% that the high rates at these ages may be due to frequent sexual activity that leads to the transmission of contaminated isolates to the area and is one of the most important risk factors for recurrent urinary tract infections as well as reproductive age, frequent pregnancy, childbirth, self-diagnosis without an appropriate prescription and delay in concomitant treatment led to an increase in the disease, menstruation and hormonal changes accompanying her and marriage [29]. Females are more susceptible than males, as gender, i.e. the physiology of the woman's body, plays a role in the inflammatory response, followed by the remaining ages, where different percentages were recorded. The differences in infections and according to ages, and in general, female infections were higher than males. It may be due to differences in innate responses to infection with age. It may be due to health practices and social and economic standards. Bacterial isolates and their types may play a role in the disparity in the percentage of infections in ages and at varying rates. It may be due to inflammatory and immune functions, and the disparity between studies is due to differences in study design, sample type, sample size, and geographical location. There is an urgent need for treatment and prevention strategies to reduce harm at all ages.

Conclusion

This study, which was conducted on urinary tract patients in Kirkuk Governorate, showed that ages 42-51 years and ages 21-32 years are the most vulnerable groups to acute, chronic and recurrent urinary tract infections.

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